

COMPETENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS: BASIS FOR PROFESSIONAL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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Competency and Performance of Public School Teachers: Basis for Professional Enhancement Program

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Abstract

This study sought to ascertain the I–III Level of Competency of Secondary Teachers and their execution. This study specifically aimed to ascertain teachers' levels of competency utilizing the Individual Performance and Results-based Performance Management System Commitment Review Form (RPMS-IPCRF), specifically: learning, pedagogy, and topic knowledge the setting and variety of students, the planning and curriculum, the evaluation and reporting, and elements. Similarly, the goal of this study was to look into the performance level of teachers. Additionally, the study aimed to explore the relationship between the caliber of teachers' performance. Furthermore, the study also sought to investigate the association between the level of teachers' competency and performance. This is a descriptive-correlational study with 99 teacher- respondents. Based on the results, all the variables led to “high” evaluation result for the competence level and “very satisfactory” for their performance. Lastly, there is no significant relationship between teachers' level of competency and their level of performance.

Keywords: *public secondary school teachers result-based performance management system – individual performance, commitment review form (RPMS-IPCRF), competency level*

Introduction

Based on NCBTS, the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers enhances the efforts to alter teacher quality from pre-service to in-service training instruction. It defines what the K–12 Reform considers to be a quality teacher using clearly stated Domains, Strands, and Indicators that offer assessments of expert knowledge and skills exercise and productive participation. These guidelines make it clear what educators should possess the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to become competent, enhance student learning outcomes, and ultimately high-quality instruction. It is based on learner-centered teaching philosophies, among other things, inclusivity and lifelong learning. As a result, Standards for teachers becomes a declaration of professional responsibility that can support educators who want to grow personally by encouraging them to evaluate and reflect on their own methods.

Today, society laments over the poor quality of basic education as reflected in the low achievement scores of Filipino students in both national and international tests. In response, the system for managing performance based on results was created by the Department of Education (DepEd). RPMS as a tool for managing performance for both non-teaching personnel and instructors. An evaluation tool that is in line with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers is called RPMS. PPST and the Civil Service's Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) Commission (CSC). Because of this, the researcher became interested in conducting this investigation aboveground and evaluate the effectiveness and degree of competency of the secondary school instructors using the results of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), whose findings would be the foundation for the creation of a training curriculum aimed at improving teacher proficiency.

The National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) play a crucial role in assessing and enhancing teacher competency and effectiveness. Studies have shown that teachers' skills complement the NCBTS, making it valuable tool for evaluating job performance (Pa-alisbo, 2017). The NCBTS framework significantly relates to critical thinking skills development among education students, with higher NCBTS competency correlating to better critical thinking abilities (Visande, 2015). Research indicates that teacher education programs based on NCBTS have a positive impact on pre-service teachers' perceptions of their teaching competencies, leading to increased confidence and improved teaching practices (Ambag, 2015). Furthermore, a study found that teachers were proficient across all NCBTS domains, with teaching effectiveness significantly correlated to all NCBTS domains. Notably, competency in curriculum was identified as the sole significant predictor of teaching effectiveness (Gultiano-Ansayam, 2020). These findings underscore the importance of NCBTS in developing competent and effective teachers.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the performance and competency of the teachers utilizing the Individual Performance and Results-based Performance Management System Form Commitment Review for school year 2019 – 2020. More so, It determine the significant relationship between teacher's level of competency and their level of performance.

Methodology

The study generally used descriptive- correlational method of research since this aimed to determine the competency level and performance of secondary teachers in Department of Education Division of Negros Oriental Manjuyod District. This further determine the association between teachers' level of competency and school performance.

The study was conducted to the 99 secondary school teachers in the Division of Negros Oriental specifically in the first congressional district where Manjuyod Districts I and II belong. District 1 comprised of three secondary schools while District II comprised of two secondary schools.

Result-based Performance Management System – Individual Performance was used to determine level of competency. Respondents responded by indicating their level of agreement on how indicative each statement was of them using a 5 point-numeric scale as 5 - strongly agree to 1 - very strongly disagree. However, the performance of the secondary school teachers was determined by the use of Commitment Review Form (RPMS-IPCRF) for school year 2019 – 2020. After collecting the instrument, the researcher tallied and tabulated the data. As such, the data were subjected to appropriate statistical treatments in order to answer the identified problems under study.

The participation of the respondents is voluntarily in nature as they have the right not to directly involve in the conduct of the study. Confidentiality of responses was strictly stressed.

Results and Discussion

Level of Competency of Secondary School Teachers

Table 1.1. *Teachers' level of competency in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy*

<i>Content Knowledge and Pedagogy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Int</i>
1.1 Applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas	2.95	.447	High
1.2 used range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in the literacy and numeral skills	2.86	.522	High
1.3 applied range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher order thinking skills	2.86	.497	High
Mean	2.89	.400	High

Table 1.1 presents the level of competency in terms of content, knowledge and pedagogy.

Notice that teachers manifest “high” level of competency as indicated in the mean of 2.89. This means that teachers have been highly integrating certain knowledge across several subjects. They also utilized varied ways of teaching for the purpose of improving students’ thinking skills that will result to better performance.

According to Gonzales (2018), it is really important for the teachers to be knowledgeable of their area of specialization and its relevance to other subjects.

As cited by Zulueta (2006), a teacher, to be effective, must possess the necessary personality attributes which include his beliefs, attitudes, philosophy, emotional maturity and his interrelationship with his students and co-teacher. He must have a high regard and appreciation to the teaching profession.

Table 1.2. *Teachers' level of competency in terms of learning environment and diversity of learners*

<i>Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Int</i>
2.1 managed classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in group, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environment	2.91	.508	High
2.2 managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environment	3.04	.462	High
2.3 used differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learner’s gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences	2.85	.618	High
Mean	2.93	.402	High

Depicted in Table 1.2 is teachers’ level of competency based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in terms of Domain 2 (Learning Environment Diversity of Learners).

Domain 2 pertains to the teachers’ competency in making the classroom environment safe and conducive to learning, establishing and maintaining consistent standard of learners’ behavior, and determining, understanding, and accepting the learners’ diverse background knowledge and experience. Relative to these competencies, teachers rated themselves “High” on all the following indicators. Overall, teachers assessed their competencies relative to Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners to be “High” as manifested in the average value of 2.93. Although the result is high, it still implies that teachers’ strengths still have to be enhanced and training needs have to be addressed as priority.

As cited by Corpuz and Salandanan (2015), it is a great challenge for teachers to make learning easy and fun for students with varying skills, abilities, interest, and personalities. Students have different levels of motivation, different attitude about teaching and learning, and different responses to specific classroom environment and instructional practices. The more thoroughly teachers understand the differences, the better chance they have of meeting the diverse needs of all their students (Felder, 2005).

Table 1.3. *Teachers' level of competency in terms of curriculum and planning*

<i>Curriculum and Planning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Int</i>
3.1 Planned, managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts	2.82	.522	High
3.2 participated in collegial discussion that used teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice	2.95	.501	High
3.3 selected, developed, organized and used appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals	3.05	.571	High
Mean	2.94	.413	High

Manifested in Table 1.3 is the teachers' level of competency based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in terms of Domain 3 (Curriculum and Planning).

Based on the data presented, it is revealed that the teachers rated themselves as "High" on all the indicators. Synthesizing the results, the teachers assessed themselves to be "High" as indicated in the average weighted mean of 2.94. Result again indicates that teachers have majority of the competencies at high level for effective teaching. It still implies a need for training.

Result of the current study is in consonance with Amores' (2012) finding wherein she likewise disclosed that teachers in the Division of Negros Oriental have a high need for training in terms of ICT skills.

Bilbao (2006) affirms that the increased use of technology in the classroom, the incorporation of the changing realities of the world's society, and the ease of mobility of people of the world become a challenge to the teachers today. Teachers should prepare to these multiple challenges. To become a global teacher, he or she must have a wider range of knowledge to keep pace with the changes brought about by the enhancement of science and technology; master skills and competencies that can address global demands; and possess attitudes and values that are acceptable to multi-cultural communities. As a teacher, he or she should think globally but act locally.

Table 1.4. *Teachers' level of competency in terms of assessment and reporting*

<i>Assessment and Reporting</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Int</i>
4.1 designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements	3.05	.549	High
4.2 monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data	2.97	.449	High
4.3 communicated promptly and clearly the learner's needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians	2.95	.525	High
Mean	2.99	.418	High

Presented in Table 1.4 is the teachers' level of competency based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in terms of Domain 4 (Assessment and Reporting).

The data clearly reveals that the teachers' level of competency in all the indicators are revealed to be "High". In general, the teachers assessed themselves to be "High" as indicated in the average weighted mean of 2.99.

Since evaluation is a part and parcel of teaching and an integral element in the proper organization of learning, it is therefore mandated under R.A. 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, the school is accountable for its performance. Schools should focus on meeting the needs of their primary clients, students, and their parents. Schools are held accountable in achieving high and improving standards of learning for all students. Thus, teachers should ensure the optimum and holistic development of learners. They should work with parents and learners to address learners' needs and promote their well-being.

Table 1.5. *Teachers' level of competency in terms of plus factor*

<i>Plus factor</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Int</i>
5.1 Performed various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process	3.01	.606	High
Mean	3.01	.606	High

Table 1.5 depicts the fifth Domain of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) which pertains to the Plus Factor.

As per result, it was revealed that the teachers rating in terms of the indicator "performed various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process" is "High" with a mean rating of 3.01. With this result, it can be viewed that aside from the main tasks expected of a teacher to perform, they also give considerable importance to other works and activities whereby developing their capability in the discharge of other tasks entrusted to them.

Furthermore, teachers have fully understood that performing various related works is part of their functions related to teaching, therefore, they devoted their time and effort in performing this function not only because it is stated in the RPMS Manual for Teachers and School Heads (2018) but it is because they fully accept this challenge as part of honing the total development of the child.

Level of Teachers' Performance

Table 2. *Performance of teachers for school year 2019 – 2020*

	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
Performance	4.07	.234	Very Satisfactory

Presented in Table 2 is the teacher-respondents' performance based on the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form of the school year 2019-2020.

As depicted, the overall performance rating of the teacher-respondents has an average rating of 4.07 which is equivalent to "very satisfactory". It can be deduced from the finding that majority of the teachers exhibits a very satisfactory performance. This result conforms to the findings of the different studies by Sabado (2014), and Catolos (2017) on DepEd Teachers having very satisfactory performance rating. This is in accordance to the expected performance of the proficient teachers who went through a lot trainings and workshops.

Association between Teachers' Competency and Performance

Table 3. *Significant relationship between teachers' level of competency and level of performance*

Variable	rho	p-value	Decision For H0	Conclusion
Overall Competency VS Performance	-.068	.549	Do not reject Ho	Not significant

For this table, the Spearman's Rho was used to test the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teacher's level of competency and level of performance. Results show that the data does not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis since the reported p-value (0.549) is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no relationship between level of competency and level of performance at 5% level of significance.

Bichi (2017) specified that evaluation of teacher performance is a continuous, routine and mandatory exercise in educational settings. Its relevance on students' learning outcomes and school accountability is enormous and cannot be underestimated. He added that the only way to determine the effectiveness of a teacher is through assessment or evaluation. Teachers are accountable in the educational process and their evaluations serve as one way to monitor and regulate accountability. Fundamental issues, the most effective way to evaluate teachers' performance and the appropriate criteria to be used in evaluating teacher's performance and effectiveness is explored by presenting the most common forms of teacher evaluation. Furthermore, this evaluation would provide valid information on the effectiveness of teacher which may serve as basis for improvement in teacher professional development, practice, policy-making and by extension lead to improved learning condition, quality education and effective learning outcomes which are the top-most priorities of goal 4 of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Conclusions

Teachers displayed adequate skills in performing their tasks and teachers performed above the minimum standards required by DepEd. Teachers' competency level does not significantly influence their performance.

The Division/District Office should create an Incentive/Award Program to encourage teachers to pursue their Graduate Studies and conduct more trainings for teachers through the Division Training and Development Staff based on the identified professional development and training/learning needs as appraised by the teachers while taking into consideration the priorities set by the school for its future development. Teachers should be required to develop an Individual Development Plan (IDP) based on the Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) and should be closely monitored by school heads as to its realization. Results of the SAT should be used as input to the School Improvement Plan (SIP) as basis for school-based capacity building of teachers. The School head must monitor the teachers every school year to maintain its performance. The school head will monitor the competency and performance every end of the school year through the use of the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for the individual teacher.

References

- Amores, A. (2012). "Teachers' Strengths and Needs Assessment Based On The National Competency-Based Teacher Standard (NCBTS) In Relation to Their Teaching Performance" Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Foundation University, Dumaguete City.
- Bichi, A. (2017). "Evaluation of Teacher Performance in Schools: Implication for Sustainable Development Goals." Northwest Journal of Educational Studies 2.1: 103-113.
- Bilbao, P. et al. (2006). The Teaching Profession. Quezon City, Philippines: Lorimar Publishing Co., Inc.
- Corpuz, B. B., & Salandanan, G. G. (2007). Principles of Teaching 1. Philippines: Lorimar Publishing, Inc. pp.11-15.
- Catolos, L., & Catolos, F. (2017). Teaching Performance of Selected Public Secondary School Teachers in Tanay, Rizal. 4th International Conference in Management Science, Innovation and Technology.
- Felder, R. M., & Brent E.R. (2005). "Understanding Student Differences", Journal of Engineering Education, An Exploration of

differences in Student's learning styles, approaches to learning and levels of intellectual Development 94 (1) 57-72).

Gonzales, A. (2018). Exploring Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) And Self Efficacy Belief of Senior High School Biology Teachers in Batangas City.

Sabado, N. (2014). The Influence of Leadership Behavior to the Teachers Performance. Dissertation. Retrieved from http://academia.edu/8219636/The_Influence_of_Leadership_Behavior_to_the_Teachers_Performance

Zulueta, F. (2006). Principles and Methods of Teaching. Mandaluyong City, Philippines: National Book Store. Teacher Competency and NCBTS Implications | Elicit 1987 Philippine Constitution, Article XIV, Sec.1. Result-based Performance Management System Manual for teachers and School Heads

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